

ISic1196

I.Sicily inscription 1196

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

basalt

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θέστωνος

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491449

EDCS 39101560

PHI 140680

PHI 175640

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0373 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. *Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelika 6*. Palermo. At 45

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5612

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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 194 no.3

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